

XX interview ICORSAKey:**I: Interviewer****R: Respondent**

I: Okay, welcome again. I am recording the interview right now. Is it possible to get your oral consent before we start?

R: Yes.

I: Thank you very much. First, I am interested to get to know your role in the [XX] project and the network a bit better so I would say we start first with your personal role in [XX]. Can you please tell me about your position and your tasks?

R: I am the director of [XX] so that means I oversee the day-to-day operations of the entire [XX] team and also I am the key contact with our funders and external partners. We are based at the university so I am also the link between the [XX] team and the university management through our head of department.

I: What makes your position special?

R: I am not sure it is special, but I suppose every organisation needs somebody to be steering the efforts of the rest of the team members. As the director, it is a special opportunity to be guiding the efforts of all the dedicated men and women that work for the group.

I: It would be very interesting to know – how did you join the network? Actually even more interesting to know – did your role change since you started and how long have you been a part of [XX]?

R: I have been a part of [XX] for about five years, on and off. I have worked for [XX] in other capacities. For example, I was at some point a researcher with the organisation, then I went away to do my postdoctoral research, I came back and applied to be the head of [XX].

I: How many years after you joined was this?

R: Do you mean how many years when I went away?

I: No. How many years after you have been a part of [XX] did you become the director?

R: I have been the director for the last one year.

I: Do you know all the other members of [XX]?

R: **[XX]** is a small organisation so maybe you are trying to refer to the network, if I know all the network members because **[XX]** is a small nuclear organisation. It is not that the network, wherever they are, is the **[XX]**. **[XX]** itself is a core nuclear organisation based in Stockholm.

I: **And you have the networks that are a part of you – IPID, ICT4SI and so on?**

R: Yes.

I: **Based on these networks then, can you please tell us if you see each other – the members of these networks – or do you exchange frequently? For example, do you have annual or monthly meetings?**

R: First of all, those networks belong to different programme areas. We have four main programme areas: research, education and learning, health, and transparency and accountability. Each programme area has a network. ICT4SI and ICT4Health are networks within the health programme and that means that the programme manager within each thematic area is in regular contact with the network participants. For me as the head of the organisation, I am therefore one step away from the day-to-day activities of the networks, but we do organise... For example, in 2017 we had an all-network meeting in Abuja in Nigeria where we brought all the network members together. Funding permitting, we also sometimes give a bit of funding so that network members in various chapters can meet among themselves so there are regular contacts with the core **[XX]** team, but it goes through different programme areas.

I: **Do you think it is important to know each other to build trust in a network and why?**

R: Yes, it is very important for them because once they know each other and they can rely on each other it enables sharing of information because a lot of this work is done in a competitive world. Each of those network members, for example, is keen to get funding from somewhere. If they don't trust each other, they can't share any information. **[XX]** being sometimes the main funder who starts these networks, if there is not trust between the members then you would have a situation where individual network members would be trying to align themselves to **[XX]** rather than to their networks.

I: **Now I would like to ask some questions on the network background and context. What was the context of emergence? You can answer this question for any of the five networks that you wish. When and why has the network been launched and what has been changing?**

R: The networks started with the oldest work programme area that **[XX]** is involved in, which is the transparency and accountability. It used to be democracy and accountability, and what was realised is that we were working with different organisations. We were funding projects that were run by different organisations, for example in East Africa, and we realised that some of the issues that were being tackled, for example by the Kenya Human Rights Commission, were the same as the issues being tackled by

another organisation in Uganda that we were funding. We realised that maybe by linking them together, they can share some of their knowledge. It was more about knowledge sharing, so we thought of having the network so that these organisations can share experiences of dealing with some of the common issues that they were tackling in different countries. Through that, the other organisations that got funding from us were encouraged to join the network. Through that experience we realised that there were a lot of synergies and the network members, through the coordination of [XX], were giving us positive feedback on some of the outcomes that they got. For example, they had joint workshops or seminars. They became a more powerful force that were then requested to take part in some of the regional events and so as the [XX] programmes grew into other thematic areas like health, we maintained the same model. Network is now our mode of operation. We do capacity building through various means that we work in. We also do research in our work, but network is also part of our way of trying to get our results and impact. It is now copied across the entire programme areas. IPID, for example, is one of the oldest networks, which was also an idea of getting together postgraduate students focusing on ICT4D, just to give them a platform where they can share their knowledge, expertise and experience in using ICT to solve some of the pertinent problems in the developing countries.

I: Your answer is forming a part of the next question. I was going to ask about the activities of the networks to work towards their objectives. For example, for IPID is there a clear role division or division of labour on who is doing what in terms of organising these activities, managing or inviting members to the events?

R: So far, that role has been done through central coordination at [XX]. What we are now doing from this month going forward is IPID has grown from when it started it was mainly postgraduate students based in Sweden who were focusing on ICT4D, but now it has grown so hugely that we have from 70 members to over 1,000 members. What we have been doing is we coordinate events from Stockholm through one coordinator based at [XX] organising events, liaising with the representatives from different areas to see how to, for example, sponsor workshops, but going forward we are now splitting it up into chapters so we are creating a southern Africa chapter, eastern Africa chapter and Asian chapter and we are working with universities from, for example, Makerere University and Wits University in South Africa to be the coordinating centres for those chapters. [XX] will contribute a small amount of money towards the activities like annual conferences or seminars and the local chapter will then be using that money to coordinate such events. If you look at IPID as an example, a lot of that coordination has been done centrally up to now. There is a point, I think... For a few years [XX] had entered into an agreement with another Swedish university, which is still on our website. We have not updated it. This university was running IPID on behalf of [XX]. Then in the last three years [XX] took it back and now we are going to split it into various chapters which will be run remotely by appointed university partners in various parts of the global south.

I: I would like to move now to the structure and format of the networks and why the networks that you have or the [XX] project has emerged have the form that they have. I mean, what are the chapters and are

there any sub-networks or subdivisions within the networks? What is the legal character of these networks? Are they classified as a company or as an association? In terms of formalisation, do they have a website, a chatroom, or do they just hold regular meetings?

R: They vary across the [XX] programmes, as I was saying. The activities and the structures differ depending on the type of network. If we take, for example, ICT4SI network, first of all they are not legal entities. They are almost like extensions of [XX] projects so they don't have a registered office and office bearers per se that are legally recognised. They are more groupings that are held together by [XX]. Yes, some of them have grown into chapters. For example, I have just given you an example of IPID, which are now splitting because it has grown bigger. ICT4SI is already split into eastern Africa and western Africa. We had funding for about three years for one person to coordinate the activities of both and we have websites hosted by [XX] for some of these networks. What happens is that then within their networks, they nominate people who, for example, moderate their chatrooms. They use a lot of social media chatrooms like WhatsApp and Facebook pages. They have those. They coordinate, for example, their chats. Somebody moderates the questions and they sometimes have online meetings through the social chatrooms. If you look at the network we have in South East Asia, mainly based in Cambodia, for the open data, they have regular meetings. They organise regular meetings with various stakeholders where they discuss topical issues of their choice and they bring together people who may be interested in a particular topic. After that, the network members then follow up with each other. If one particular organisation wanted help, maybe with experts in coding, for example – computer coding – then through the network meeting they share ideas and they probably get an expert in that area that then the organisation can liaise with, whether it is on a paid basis or a voluntary basis. The key thing is that we promote knowledge sharing and expertise sharing. Because the funding is very limited, we can't push them into doing a lot of things like regular meetings because then those call for paid, salaried staff, which at the moment we can't afford. It is not a structured, legal, formal process, but they do have their own meetings, whether remotely or in physical spaces depending on the network, and from there they get to widen the network by including more members and also probably by looking for more resources elsewhere to continue with their activities.

I: **My next question is about the structure of the network again. You can just pick one of the networks – ICT4SI or IPID – and maybe give an example on that, but we would like to know what has been changed meanwhile and why? Was there any key moments or decisions?**

R: The structure is not straightforward if you are looking at it from a point of view of organisational structure per se because the way they are run, they don't quite fit into an organisational structure that would be well laid out, but as I say, at the top of it you have somebody at [XX] in Stockholm. Let's say the ICT4Health programme. The programme manager for health would be at the top and then you have some volunteer who is coordinating the local activities, communicating with members and moderating members' issues between the membership and [XX]. When it comes to the question of what has changed, the two things that have changed, as I have mentioned, is two of the networks have grown too big to be one. The splitting is a change

because we moved from having one person coordinating the activities to having two people coordinating different chapters – for example, ICT4SI West Africa and ICT4SI East Africa. Still both coordinators report back to the programme manager who is in charge of that particular network. The other change that has taken place, especially with ICT for Democracy and Accountability, is that [XX]'s focus moved from supporting projects that campaign for democratic rights and what I would call advocacy towards more use of open data to achieve the same thing. That particular network had to evolve from being a network of advocates that maybe championed for change on the streets to advocates for free, fair and accessible data. Their focus changed from a change that [XX]'s programme underwent.

I: So it has adapted itself for the changing focus of [XX] from democracy to open access data, which is a big pillar of RRI. This was a great answer. Thank you. Do you know who decided to choose this structure for these networks? Did you have a common structure for any of these groupings that have been emerging or receiving funding from [XX] to start a network? Were there any alternatives or has the structure been changed? Is any of these networks' model based on any other network model that you took as an example?

R: No. We just looked at our name, [XX], and we looked at the [XX] animal. We saw a web and we thought of creating a web of partners that we work with. Then as we work in different areas, we are just creating a web of partners in each thematic area. It is more of [XX]'s own inspiration from the name, which has nothing to do with the animal [XX], but we borrowed from nature and we decided that every project that we fund, partners in that particular area would be encouraged to be part of the network in that area. If there was an inspiration, then it is from the animal [XX].

I: When you think about the [XX] model, then, can you give any pros and cons of this specific model based on your experience regarding aims, membership, funding and geographic spread?

R: One of the downsides with our network is that we actually don't have a structure, aims and objectives, and laid out roles and responsibilities. We have reached a point where we are now thinking of, okay, we have these networks. They have grown. What do we do with them? That is the current discussion we are having because some of the members are very enthusiastic and so they are wondering, what do we do? Yes, we are in a network. We have joined. What do we do? The other downside is that by default, the partners that we fund as opposed to probably feel interest in joining networks in some of the programme areas, but then some of the projects we fund through organisations in America who probably... Not just America, but as an example, if a project is funded through an organisation in the US, they are most likely not going to be interested in being in some network in West Africa, even though it may be a project that falls under health. That has brought us into a situation where we are thinking of where do we want to go with the networks? Also the fact that organisations join because they are funded. Sometimes they dilute the strength of the network because some people just join because [XX] is providing support and it is cool to do what [XX] is supporting, but they actually aren't keen on being in the network. We have not been told this, but this is now my interpretation.

Some people are going to join just because [XX] has this network, but they are not keen and that means that the synergies that networks are supposed to generate are not realised. We also see that yes, we found networks, yet we don't have money to support these networks going forward. For example, to have proper coordination you need somebody who can be running things and we can't afford to keep people on salaries to run things. Those are some of the downsides or the challenges with our networks, but I also have to add that there have been success stories where some network members have gone on to form partnerships and have been able to get funding to do other things that they want beyond the network, so the network has been like a stepping stone for them to do some other, bigger things that they want to do.

I: Diversity and gender are some of the frequently discussed topics. Do you have implementation of specific structures or policies – for example, parity in decision making bodies, positions etc. – formal or informal mechanisms for gender and diversity dynamics in [XX]?

R: In [XX] itself or in the networks?

I: You can answer this question for any of the networks that are connected to [XX] if you wish.

R: Gender is something that we focus on a lot. As you may know, Sweden is one of the main countries that is pushing for gender equality through its own government and the government structures. Sweden is one of the countries that is highly female focused, if I may use that word, but also generally gender focused so as an organisation in Sweden right from where we are, gender is something that is running across our operations and that means that even with our partners, it is something that we ask for when they submit applications: to explain how, for example, the leadership is gender focused and gender balanced, but also more importantly, how the people who the projects are going to benefit are also... there is a focus on the gender of the beneficiaries, if I may use the word beneficiaries though we don't use it a lot because we don't believe we are just working with people who are waiting to benefit. But back to your question, as an organisation how we are structured here, how we are staffed and also how we work with our partners, things like gender, things like inclusion are very key. For the projects we fund, we ask our partners to clearly state how, for example, the project will benefit people with disabilities and people who are marginalised sexual minorities. That then filters through into the networks because the organisations then have an awareness that, for example, the representation... If we have network meetings, we just don't have the same people going to the same meetings in the course of their role, but having representation in those kinds of meetings. For example, recently – just last month – [XXX] had their – it's called internet forum – where they invite all their partners across the world that work in development initiatives, and [XX] being one of the major [XXX] partners, we nominate our partners or our network members to come to this event. In that case, we do representation both geographic and gender and ability and all that. Our networks are not 100 per cent perfect, but by default fall along the same lines of our working ethos.

I: Would you say that awareness of gender and diversity contribute to the success or the effectiveness of these networks?

R: It contributes to the effectiveness of the networks in the sense that the networks become also a means of keeping that dialogue going. As much as the networks may be focusing on, for example, access to public information, that access to public information also focuses on gender and inclusion as key issues. The way I see it, it is not because that focus makes the networks effective, but that focus makes the networks part of the means towards achieving diversity and inclusion.

I: **Now I would like to speak a little bit more about the members of these networks and the membership models. What is the range of membership options: individual members versus member associations or members associated to an organisation, different levels of benefits or rights, or different roles?**

R: I think our networks are mainly formed through organisations so members are drawn from the organisations we work with. Because our networks, as I say, developed through the projects that we fund and because we don't fund individuals, all the network members then are affiliated to the organisations that we work with and they join as representatives of those organisations. What we have realised is that sometimes when the membership grows, it becomes individual. Sometimes it is individuals – a social entrepreneur with an idea in Nigeria who then joins the network. They may join as an individual, but they also represent probably their idea that may be evolving into an organisation in future. That is different with IPID. IPID is more of individual membership as long as they are postgraduate researchers in ICT4D. Roles and responsibilities and sharing of resources as you asked – as I said earlier on, that is something that is still very loose. We have worked with individual persons in certain organisations that we have funded that we requested to coordinate the activities of the networks. We have contributed to salaries of individuals in specific organisations who then coordinate the activities of the network. The salaried individual, whether it is 20 per cent of their time, becomes the focal point and organise the rest of the membership.

I: **Are there gender, minorities and multicultural aspects in your memberships?**

R: Yes. As you probably have read, we work in very different, many countries in the global south where multiculturalism is almost a norm, unlike in Europe where multiculturalism has to be promoted. We work with people from diverse backgrounds and also the aspect of inclusion, as I said, is now a big part of our work. We try and work with our partners in every single project to emphasise inclusion and we see it through the networks as well that there is different representation from different demographics in the communities where our projects are based.

I: **Which rights or tasks do network members have? For example, do they have the right to vote or decision making? Is there a hierarchy and how is this conceived? Do you have different categories of monetary contributions?**

R: Rights and tasks are the things that I was telling you earlier on that we are now thinking how to come up with ways that could make those very clear because the networks have grown and therefore there is a need for

somebody to lead and somebody to have some clearly defined roles. We don't have elections of board members or leadership or things like that. We don't have those at the moment in our networks. In terms of contributions, whatever goes into those networks comes from [XX], which is funded as a project. As I said, it is mainly towards the network activities – for example, contributing towards the costs of a network conference. This happens a lot with IPID, for example. We have annual conferences that we finance individual members to attend or we co-fund the venue or refreshments. It is nothing structured, per se. If you are looking at a structured way of funding or leadership or election of officials, those are the things that we want to work on now to see how to deal with them because as I mentioned, that is one of the weaknesses of our networks: that there is no proper role or duty assigned to any particular individual.

I: We are aiming to form a global network called the RRING to mainly communicate the RRI practices. As you know, RRI is emerging more in Europe, but it is not limited to Europe. It is being used globally, but it may be conceived differently in different regions of the world. As a global network, we are also looking for the best management structure to find out. Just like you declared that lack of structure is a weakness of your networks, we are also interviewing many networks to see what are the best structures. I assume you would be interested to see the results of what type of structure makes a good network. Hopefully once we have the results from the interviews we will be able to share with you so you can also benefit from this.

R: Thank you.

I: For the next question, in your opinion, why do members choose to join a network? Why do network members participate? Are there any incentives for participation as a member?

R: In our case, it is a common goal – when they have a common goal and when they realise that they have a common goal, but there is also something that can be of benefit to them as individual members. I think one of the other motivations for [XX] network membership is just the desire to make a change. I think most of the organisations, because everything we do is linked to ICT for development so there is a common thread in everything that all the network partners do, that common goal and wanting to make a difference in some of the areas that we work because we fund ICT for the accessibility to those who are most in need. I think there is a common desire there throughout the entire network, whether it is IPID or ICT4SI. It is to solve problems for the people who are almost marginalised. I think that common interest is a big driver.

I: Now I would like to move to part 4, which is more questions on the network funding model. I have some more questions on more concrete managerial issues, in particular how the governance or management of your network is structured, but also the funding sources that you employ. You could answer these questions for [XX] in terms of receiving funding or how do you provide funding for all of these networks or conferences and activities. Can you please tell me which

sources you utilise for funding: membership, project funding, national grants, philanthropy, SME based, consultancy or other?

R: We are a public organisation. We get all our funding from Swedish development agency and it is that money that – some of it – we use to fund our network activities.

I: **[XXX] agency, did you say?**

R: Yes, [XXX] Agency – [XXX].

I: **Do you know if [XX] has an annual budget?**

R: We do have an annual budget, yes.

I: **Does the network have longer term budget projections – for example, five-year, three-year?**

R: We are a five-year programme. We do that considering activities for the networks and then that is broken down into an annual budget so every year we decide how much money we want to spend on the networks depending on our overall budget. Most of our money goes into projects so as much as we allocate a small amount to the networks, still these network members also have funding for projects. I suppose we may spend significantly little money on network activities, but the fact that we are funding these organisations to run projects also motivates them to keep engaging with the network.

I: **How important is the funding to [XX]? How much resources are dedicated in [XX] to secure more funding?**

R: What do you mean?

I: **How much resources are dedicated to accounting?**

R: Accounting, managing the finances we have?

I: **Yes, or when you receive funding, do you devote some of this funding to secure more funding?**

R: Yes, because we pay for staff time to go chasing more funding and make other applications. A significant amount of our funding goes to staff salaries who then work hard to secure more funding. We don't have a budget for funding application.

I: **For the governance and management structure, can you please tell me in detail again who has managing responsibilities in [XX]? What do different bodies do? For example, do you have a board of directors for [XX], executive committee, advisory board?**

R: We have a board of directors, we have a director and then we have programme managers, then we have programme coordinators and we have admins. We have a general structure that most other organisations would have or a department at a university would have. We have a director and deputy director at the [XX] level, then each programme area is headed by a programme manager, and a few people under each programme area. Of course we have a board of directors who are non-salaried. We don't have a salaried board of directors.

I: **Do you also have a principal committee member board: chair, co-chair, vice chair, secretary, treasurer?**

R: We have just a chair of the board.

I: **Can you please describe rotation mechanisms or what expertise is required to be on the board or the committees?**

R: First of all, they have to be people who are interested in the use of ICT for development. That is the underlying requirement. It can't be just somebody who has no clue about what ICT can do for development. They could come from various backgrounds, whether it is health, whether it is social innovation, whether it is education. The underlying thing is that they have to be people who have knowledge and expertise in the use of ICT for international development.

I: **Regarding communication, do you have regular management meetings? How frequent and what do you discuss there?**

R: When you say management meetings, what do you mean? That may mean different things depending on the size of the organisation.

I: **For [XX], regarding communication. How do you communicate if there is going to be an event or if there is a decision to be made?**

R: Your question is not very clear because if there is an event then we make it known through different outlets. First of all, we are part of the university so we have university structures for communication. At [XX] we also have our own communication channels including our own web page. We have our mailing lists, we have the entire [XX] network so we can send one email to all the networks and that would send things through, but if you talk about meetings or things like that then it is not something that is necessarily communicated through those networks unless you are referring to a decision from either a board meeting or a team meeting or a university management meeting. Then it is communicated appropriately depending on the audience of the decision.

I: **It answers both parts, but I mainly mean an AGM. Usually networks or organisations have an annual general meeting. Do you have any meetings like that for [XX]?**

R: That is where probably you meet the point I mentioned earlier on. When you talk about [XX] networks, [XX] is an organisation. [XX] itself it not a network.

I: **Maybe we can say [XX] (over speaking)**

R: [XX] has a network around it so as I explained before, we have networks around the work we do. We are not a network, but we have a network that we manage that is formed around the work we do. We don't have an annual general meeting of these many organisations that form [XX]. What we do is we organise network meetings whenever funding allows and those network meetings are not your equivalent of an AGM where decisions are made. They are more about sharing experiences and sharing resources and network, thinking of how to help each other to solve certain problems. That is probably the confusion, because [XX] itself is not a network of organisations – [XX] is a centre at the University of [X].

I: **Thank you for making this clear again. How do you measure and monitor the effectiveness of your networks that are connected to [XX]? What is effectiveness to you? Which management mechanisms are important to promote the effectiveness of a network?**

R: We don't go into that technical management language with our networks, but some of the things we use to measure effectiveness include, for example, the successful addition of funding sources that our network partners get. We also look out for things, for example government endorsing some initiatives by network members, which we have a few reported. Those are some of the things that we are also thinking about – how do we report and monitor success of the networks? That is one of the discussions we are having now.

I: **Does any of the networks connected to [XX] have a five-year road map or a Gantt chart and is this publicly available?**

R: They have their road maps, but not necessarily five-year road maps.

I: **And are they publicly available, for example on the website? Is it possible for us to retrieve it?**

R: I doubt so. Probably not because as I said, again we are not that structured network in that sense. Those are some of the things that we are trying to now think about going to into next year – how to structure everything. The networks are more groups of organisations with a common interest and for some reason they have ended up getting some funding from [XX] and therefore they are meeting to carry on the work that they do, but also networking to see if they can support each other with information and expertise.

I: **We are coming to the last few questions.**

R: How last, because I need to run away? I need to go to another meeting.

I: **Is there a risk and mitigation plan for any of the networks?**

R: No. That will probably come up when we have the structures that you are looking for. We don't have those now.

I: Do all the network members receive the same information in your email lists, for example, or is there any difference?

R: Yes. We mainly communicate through social media outlets so all members subscribing to that would see the same information.

I: Trust issues between directors. How do you think trust is established and maintained? Which challenges are faced due to cultural differences between management boards or are there any conflicts between members of the networks and their affiliation to an organisation?

R: In terms of conflicts, not that I know of, but the first part of the question doesn't apply to us because our networks don't have management boards and directors.

I: The last few questions on the challenges and problems with the networks. What kind of problems did any of these networks face? Do you know something about that? For example, potential difficulties could be were there any cases where the network members have dropped out or do you know why? Was this a problem for a network or were there any problems with members adhering to the network identity?

R: Again, that question is more of a network that is more structured than the [XX] one, but we have had cases where network members have not necessarily dropped out, but have stopped engaging more actively because as I said, one of the things is that when going into networks some people expect, for example, extra funding and they don't get that extra funding so then they go looking for it somewhere else. In terms of engagement, it requires time commitment and in our case where the network doesn't have any straightforward funding structure and people have to do other things to survive in their organisation, the engagement sometimes gets weak.

I: Which challenges are faced due to cultural differences – differences in notions of collectivity and collaboration?

R: That one is something that probably is not yet very clear to us because our networks are based in places where diversity is not such a big thing to be naturally the way it is probably in Europe where you need to include minorities and all that. It is a difficult thing to answer from our network perspective.

I: Are there any conflicts with members of the networks and their affiliation to an organisation, for example when their organisation's objectives are not in line with those of the network?

R: No, because our networks are not yet binding and legally holding so people don't feel that they are threatened.

I: If you could warn us about any potential pitfalls, is there anything general or specific that we should be aware of when we want to establish our global network? What would it be. This is the final question, by the way.

R: I think the pitfall with what you are trying to do is for example, looking at this... Your RRING project, I don't know, but from what I am reading it is also PACT, the European Research Funding Council, you are trying to get previous researchers who have gone through that programme and I think the pitfall is what is the long-term view? That is what we are finding with our network. What is the long-term view? For example, right now it is sexy to form a network of good research practice, but what is the long-term view for individuals? In our case, what is the long-term benefit for the organisations in joining the network? It may be nice now to form a network of researchers and good research practice, but 5-10 years from now what is the benefit of being in that for members? How will the older members benefit compared to the new members? That is just lessons from our own networks because it is nice when it starts, but then as it grows, what next?

I: That is it. We went through all the questions. Thank you very much for sharing your experience and in particular taking time for this interview. Is there anything we didn't speak about or any other issues that you would like to raise?

R: In trying to get this network going, what is RRING? Who is RRING targeting actually to be network members?

I: Individuals, organisations, universities, NGOs. It will be a diverse range of memberships.

R: That are involved in research in general or that are involved in European funded research?

I: It could be many categories of networks – for example, research promoting organisations, research funding organisations – but we can provide more information in detail if you wish.

R: No, just a question that probably is answered so that is fine.

I: Do you have any further comments or questions?

R: No. That is all I have to say for now.

I: Thank you very much for taking the time and have a good day. Goodbye.

R: Bye.

(End of recording)